

HORIZON 2020

Research and Innovation action

Grant Agreement No. 730965

ARICE: Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium:

**A strategy for meeting the needs for marine-based research
in the Arctic**

Deliverable 3.3

Webinar recording on Data Management

Submission of Deliverable

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Lead Beneficiary	AP (Halldór Jóhannsson)
Contributors	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 1 – AWI, <input type="checkbox"/> 2 – SPRS, <input type="checkbox"/> 3 - NPI, <input type="checkbox"/> 4 - ULAVAL, <input type="checkbox"/> 5 – UAF/CFOS, <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 6 – AP, <input type="checkbox"/> 7 – CSIC-UTM, <input type="checkbox"/> 8 – CNR, <input type="checkbox"/> 9 - WOC, <input type="checkbox"/> 10 – IOPAN, <input type="checkbox"/> 11 – FMI, <input type="checkbox"/> 12 - CNRS, <input type="checkbox"/> 13 – NERC-BAS, <input type="checkbox"/> 14 – DTU-AQUA
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Executive Summary

In the frame of WP3 “Educating a new generation of polar researchers and professionals”, APECS and Arctic Portal held a webinar as part of ARICE and as deliverable 3.3 with the topic “Data Management” on 17 December 2019.

The aim of this webinar is to provide an overview of current statuses in data management, policy, planning and best practices as well as advances in data presentation, integration and interpretation.

The webinar was introduced through ARICE, APECS and Arctic Portal outreach channels including websites and social media.

Four invited expert speakers presented:

Halldór Jóhannsson, Executive Director of [Arctic Portal](#), member of SAON steering group, co-lead of communication in the EU Polar Cluster and leader of WP 7 within ARICE;

Anseok Joo, Programmer at Arctic Portal;

Stein Sandven, director of the Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center, co-lead of the Data Management in the EU Arctic Cluster and project coordinator of [INTAROS](#) (Integrated Arctic Observation System);

Øystein Godøy, senior scientist, data manager at the Norwegian Meteorological Institute and co-lead of the Data Management in the EU Arctic Cluster.

56 participants registered in advance to the webinar with 22 actively attending, due to timing issues.

A follow-up sessions is being planned in February to accommodate other time zones as North America and to further introduce and elaborate on the 3D icebreaker data management system.

The webinar was recorded and is now available on the ARICE website.

<https://arice.eu/training/webinars/84-arice-webinar-data-management>

Webinar on Data Management

The webinar on Data Management is deliverable 3.3 in the ARICE project.

This webinar was the second out of a planned webinar series of minimum four within the ARICE project.

The aim of this webinar is to provide an overview of current statuses in data management, policy, planning and best practices as well as advances in data presentation, integration and interpretation.

The webinar was held using Zoom technology on December 17, 2019 from 09-10.30 GMT.

Speakers and presentation topics

As speakers, we invited researchers and professionals with experience in data management, namely:

Halldór Jóhannsson, Executive Director of [Arctic Portal](#), member of SAON steering group, co-lead of communication in the EU Polar Cluster and leader of WP 7 within ARICE, gave an overview

introduction and touched on topics of policy and best practice of data management, as well as engagement with stakeholders.

Anseok Joo, Programmer at Arctic Portal, discussed topics of data presentation and the ARICE 3D Icebreaker, including a live demonstration on mapping, data presentation, integration and interpretation.

Stein Sandven, director of the Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center, co-lead of the Data Management in the EU Arctic Cluster and project coordinator of [INTAROS](#) (Integrated Arctic Observation System), spoke about the INTAROS data management practices with emphasis on meta data and federated search. He expanded his presentation on the Assessment of existing Arctic observing systems and data

Øystein Godøy, senior scientist, data manager at the Norwegian Meteorological Institute and co-lead of the Data Management in the EU Arctic Cluster provided further perspectives of APPLICATE, SIOS and NorDataNet.

Participants

56 participants registered in advance to the webinar, but some of them (namely from USA) could not connect due to the huge time difference, as the webinar was held from 09-10.30 GMT, and asked for the webinar recording.

It is intended to offer another webinar on data management with a more favourable time for North-American participants, likely in February 2020.

On the webinar day, 22 participants actually connected, 21 of them based at European countries (12 in Germany!) and only 1 at non-European country (China), taking the opportunity to listen and raise questions on data management issues.

Nationalities of the participants attending the webinar.

Germany	12
UK	4
Norway	1
France	1
Poland	1
Denmark	1
Ukraine	1
China	1

Discussion and feedback

A few questions were asked during the presentation, e.g. a participant asked how many requests for Arctic Data are received and what is the share of non-academic (governmental, industrial) requests. Also one participant asked for a link to the INTAROS survey.

Finally, it was also asked whether a recording of the webinar is available and few “thank you” notes were sent before the webinar ended.

Link to the Webinar

This webinar was the second out of a webinar series of four.

A recording as well as the presented slides are freely available on the ARICE website:

<https://arice.eu/training/webinars/84-arice-webinar-data-management>